

FROM ORIGIN TO END: BLOCKCHAIN FOR SEAMLESS PRODUCT AUTHENTICATION AND OWNERSHIP VERIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

Counterfeiting poses a significant threat to global supply chains, undermining consumer trust, compromising public safety, and eroding brand value. Traditional methods such as serial number serialization and holograms, while tamper-resistant, require more robust, scalable solutions. This paper presents "Proof Point," a blockchain-based anti-counterfeiting system that leverages the Ethereum blockchain to ensure product authenticity and ownership tracking. By creating a decentralized, tamper-proof ledger, Proof Point enables real-time verification of product authenticity through QR codes linked to unique blockchain records. Smart contracts automate key processes such as product registration and ownership transfers, minimizing manual intervention and reducing fraud risks. To enhance performance, a local database stores metadata for fast and efficient access without dependency on external services. The decentralized architecture ensures secure tracking from manufacturers to end consumers, offering scalable applications across industries such as pharmaceuticals, electronics, and luxury goods. Although high transaction costs remain a challenge on Ethereum, future iterations aim to integrate cost-effective scaling solutions. Proof Point provides a transparent, reliable, and efficient mechanism for mitigating counterfeiting risks, fostering trust in supply chains, and supporting long-term resilience.

Keywords: Blockchain, anti-counterfeiting, supply chain security, smart contracts, Proof Point.

Cite this Article: Vraj Shah, Mahir Modi, Manas Raval. (2024). From Origin to End: Blockchain for Seamless Product Authentication and Ownership Verification. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology*, 15(6), 46–57.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJARET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_6/IJARET_15_06_004.pdf

1. INTRODUCTION

Global supply chains are increasingly vulnerable to cross-border threats, particularly from the proliferation of counterfeit goods. These threats have a profound impact on brand integrity, consumer trust, and public safety. Counterfeit pharmaceuticals, for example, pose severe health risks, potentially leading to fatal consequences, while fake electronics may malfunction, causing electrical hazards, fires, or accidents. Even counterfeit luxury goods, though less life-threatening, result in significant economic losses, diminishing the value and exclusivity of premium brands. Traditional methods, such as serial numbers, holograms, and physical checks, though widely adopted, remain highly susceptible to forgery. This inability to counter the rising sophistication of counterfeiters highlights the urgent need for innovative, reliable solutions that can ensure product authenticity at every stage of the supply chain.

The limitations of these conventional techniques underscore the pressing demand for a robust and comprehensive approach that combines transparency, security, and accountability. This paper aims to address these challenges by exploring advanced technological interventions that strengthen supply chain integrity and enhance consumer confidence. By leveraging modern innovations, this research envisions a counterfeit-resistant ecosystem capable of mitigating risks and ensuring that public trust, brand value, and product authenticity are safeguarded. In doing so, it lays the foundation for the development of a transformative solution to counter global supply chain threats effectively.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Blockchain technology demonstrates promising abilities in attaining transparency, security, and traceability in various industries. Many studies have been conducted in the context of counterfeiting prevention and management supply chain.

2.1. Product Ownership Management

Toyoda et al. [1] introduced a blockchain-based Product Ownership Management System (POMS) designed to record product movements and provide real-time transparency. By maintaining an immutable ledger of ownership changes, the system effectively safeguards against counterfeit products entering the supply chain. Building on this, Wang et al. [9] demonstrated the use of smart contracts to establish a robust product traceability system, emphasizing their automation and efficiency in securing tamper-proof transaction records. These studies form a strong foundation for systems like ProofPoint, which leverage similar principles to enhance product authenticity verification and streamline supply chain processes.

2.2. NFC in Supply Chains

Alzahrani and Bulusu et al. [2] integrated blockchain with NFC to propose a safe supply chain framework. This method suggests that the tamper-proof nature of blockchain can be utilized to verify products while they are in transit. This way, counterfeit products would not have the opportunity to get into the marketplace.

2.3. Comparison of Consensus Mechanisms

Cao et al. [3] have compared different blockchain consensus mechanisms like PoW (Proof of Work) and PoS (Proof of Stake). Their study elucidates the trade-offs among security, scalability, and energy consumption when considering optimisation for blockchain-based anticounterfeiting systems.

Blockchain for Agriculture

Salah et al. [4] demonstrated the traceability of blockchain in tracing a product across its entire supply chain from its production to point of consumption. Shahid et al. [5] have expanded these findings into building a framework that would, essentially embed assurance on the food safety and transparency through the agri-food supply chain.

2.5. Decentralized Supply Chain Management

Bencić et al. [6] had presented a decentralized system of supply chain based on DLT and smart tags. Their work merges smart contracts to ensure product verification and bypass data privacy issues while retaining control over authenticity.

2.6. Reputation Systems for Retail

Liu et al. [7] Develop a blockchain-based anonymous reputation system of retail, allowing trust without compromising anonymity. Their study illustrates the feasibility of blockchain in the context of retail environments regarding efficiency and security. Blockchain significantly reduces the risk of counterfeiting by creating decentralized and immutable records, as highlighted by Cui et al. [8]. Their research underscores the importance of trust and accountability within supply chains, which rely on secure and transparent proof of product authenticity. Similarly, Upadhyay et al. [10] examined the connection between blockchain technology and the circular economy, highlighting its potential to enhance sustainability and social responsibility. Their findings reveal that blockchain improves traceability while fostering trust among stakeholders, making it an essential tool for building environmentally and socially conscious supply chains.

2.7. ProofPoint's Innovation

With these works as inspiration, the ProofPoint system ensures that it offers a scalable anti-counterfeiting solution by applying blockchain with an on-device database. With the help of fast access to data, the systems ensure products can be verified in real time through QR codes, as well as ownership tracking that fights cross-industry counterfeiting

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

3.1. Existing System

In current supply chains, product authenticity is mainly governed through manual processes like serial numbers, holograms, or physical inspections. Although widely used, these mechanisms can easily be forged or tampered with. Centralized databases, which hold product information, are prone to hacking attacks, corruption, and manipulation by unintended entities. Consequently, the information stored in such databases may not be reliable. Verification processes are also time-consuming, causing delays that disrupt operations and frustrate customers.

Intermediaries such as wholesalers, distributors, and third party logistics companies increase the risk of counterfeit products infiltrating the supply chain. Consumers have limited means to confirm a product's authenticity, often relying solely on manufacturers' claims or simple packaging indicators that can be easily reproduced. Several industries—particularly pharmaceuticals, luxury goods, and electronics—have reported significant financial losses and safety risks from counterfeit products. Current systems lack real-time transparency, making it difficult for consumers and businesses to track the history and ownership of products effectively.

3.2. Disadvantages

Traditional product tracking and verification systems have several major disadvantages that undermine their effectiveness. One significant issue is the Lack of Transparency, as centralized databases restrict equal access to information among stakeholders, leading to reduced trust between manufacturers, retailers, and consumers. These systems are also Vulnerable to Tampering, as centralized structures are prone to cyber-attacks that can compromise the integrity of product data. Additionally, Time-Consuming Verification processes often slow down the confirmation of product authenticity, causing unnecessary delays. Inefficient Ownership Tracking further complicates matters, as tracking ownership changes across multiple entities becomes difficult without a unified system. Insecure Physical Checks, such as holograms and other physical indicators, can be easily duplicated, making traditional verification methods unreliable. The involvement of multiple Intermediaries increases the chances of counterfeit goods entering the market, further eroding product authenticity. Finally, these challenges contribute to Consumer Mistrust, as poor verification mechanisms reduce confidence in the authenticity of products, discouraging consumers from trusting the supply chain.

4. PROPOSED SOLUTIONS

To address these challenges, the ProofPoint project proposes a blockchain-based anti-counterfeiting system that ensures product authenticity and ownership verification throughout the supply chain. ProofPoint leverages the decentralized and immutable nature of blockchain along with a local database to create an efficient, secure, and scalable solution. Below are the key components forming the core of the system:

4.1. System Architecture

The architecture of the Proof Point system emphasizes transparency, efficiency, and security in tracking product transactions and verifying authenticity.

The ProofPoint system integrates several cutting-edge technologies to ensure product authenticity, traceability, and the overall efficiency of the supply chain. At its core, the **Blockchain Ledger** utilizes the Ethereum blockchain, which plays a crucial role in providing a secure, tamper-proof, and transparent record of all product transactions. This decentralized system captures every transaction along the product's journey, from its manufacturing to the final sale, ensuring that the entire product lifecycle remains fully traceable. Once the transaction data is recorded on the blockchain, it becomes immutable and cannot be altered or deleted, creating an unchangeable history of product ownership. This enhances transparency and builds trust among all parties involved in the supply chain. To further enable traceability, each product is assigned a unique **QR Code**, which is linked directly to its blockchain record. Consumers and stakeholders can easily scan this QR code using a mobile application to access real-time information about the product's origin, ownership history, certifications, and other essential details. This functionality empowers consumers to make well-informed purchasing decisions,

significantly reducing the risk of counterfeit goods entering the market and enhancing the overall trustworthiness of the supply chain. In addition, the ProofPoint system leverages **Smart Contracts** to automate critical supply chain processes such as product registration, ownership transfer, and verification. These contracts are executed automatically when specific conditions are met, such as the confirmation of payment, without the need for intermediaries. This automation minimizes fraud risks, reduces operational delays, and ensures that the terms of each transaction are transparent and enforceable, fostering trust and collaboration among all stakeholders. Furthermore, while blockchain offers exceptional transparency and security, it is not ideal for storing large volumes of metadata. To address this limitation, ProofPoint integrates a **Local Database** to store non-critical product information, such as product descriptions, specifications, images, and other related details. This hybrid approach ensures that critical product information can be accessed quickly and efficiently, without overloading the blockchain with excessive data. The local database works in conjunction with the blockchain to provide real-time updates of product records, maintaining a seamless flow of information while optimizing the system's performance. By combining the strengths of blockchain, smart contracts, and local databases, the ProofPoint system offers a scalable and efficient solution that can be applied across various industries, ensuring both the security of product data and the smooth operation of the supply chain.

Fig. 1 Architecture Diagram of Proof Point System

4.2. Workflow

The ProofPoint system provides a streamlined workflow, ensuring that every stage of the product lifecycle is trackable and verifiable. Step 1: Product Registration Manufacturers register products by generating unique QR codes linked to blockchain records. Product metadata, such as origin, specifications, and certifications, is stored in the local database,

providing each product with a tamper-proof digital identity. Step 2: Ownership Transfer Ownership changes—whether from manufacturers to distributors or from retailers to consumers—are recorded on the blockchain through smart contracts. These transactions occur in real time, ensuring that the latest ownership status is always available. Fig. 2. Workflow Step 3: Consumer Verification Consumers use the ProofPoint mobile application to scan the QR code on the product packaging. The scan retrieves the blockchain record and displays the product’s authenticity, ownership history, and relevant certifications. This process helps consumers verify the product before purchase, reducing the risk of buying counterfeit goods.

Fig. 2 Workflow Diagram of ProofPoint System

4.3. Major Advantages of the Proposed Solution

The ProofPoint system provides several distinct advantages over traditional product tracking and verification methods, enhancing both efficiency and trust throughout the supply chain. **Enhanced Transparency** is achieved through the decentralized blockchain ledger, which ensures that all stakeholders, from manufacturers to consumers, have equal access to accurate product information. **Improved Security** is guaranteed by blockchain's tamper-proof nature, ensuring that product data remains unaltered and reliable. Additionally, **Automated Processes** through smart contracts streamline critical operations like ownership transfers and product verification, eliminating the need for manual interventions and reducing the risk of human error. **Real-Time Verification** is facilitated by QR code scanning, offering instant access to product records and ensuring authenticity is quickly confirmed. This contributes to **Reduced Counterfeit Risk**, as the immutable record of ownership makes it much harder for counterfeit goods to enter the supply chain. The system also offers **Cost Efficiency** by automating processes and reducing the need for intermediaries, which helps to lower operational costs. Finally, **Scalability** ensures that the ProofPoint system can be applied across various industries, including pharmaceuticals, electronics, and luxury goods, adapting to different supply chain needs and offering a versatile solution for counteracting counterfeiting on a global scale.

4.4. Challenges and Future Improvements

While the ProofPoint system provides a robust solution, it faces several challenges that need to be addressed for broader adoption and scalability. One of the key challenges is the limited transaction throughput of Ethereum, which may hinder scalability, though future versions could integrate layer-2 solutions like rollups to enhance performance. Additionally, high gas fees on the Ethereum network could impact profitability, especially for small businesses, prompting the exploration of hybrid blockchain models or alternative platforms to lower costs. Another critical challenge is user adoption, as educating stakeholders about blockchain technology and the use of QR codes is crucial for ensuring widespread acceptance and seamless integration across industries. Addressing these challenges will be key to maximizing the system's potential and ensuring its long-term sustainability.

4.5. Workflow

The proposed workflow of the ProofPoint system is designed to ensure transparency, security, and efficiency throughout the product lifecycle. First, during Product Registration, manufacturers assign a unique QR code to each product, linking it to essential information such as ownership records and transaction history, all of which is securely recorded on the blockchain. This enables easy access and verification of product details, significantly enhancing transparency and building trust within the supply chain. Next, during Ownership Transfer, the entire transaction is automatically recorded in the blockchain smart contract when a product is sold or transferred. This ensures that the transaction record is tamper-proof and accurate. The updated transaction details are reflected in the QR code, allowing stakeholders to verify the product's ownership history at any point. This process establishes a transparent and immutable chain of custody, reassuring stakeholders about the product's authenticity and fostering confidence in its origin. Finally, for Consumer Verification, the ProofPoint application allows consumers to scan the product's QR code, which opens the blockchain record. The user-friendly app provides quick access to essential information such as authentication status, ownership history, and other relevant product details. By providing easy and immediate access to verified data, the application empowers consumers to make informed purchasing decisions, ensuring they can confidently verify the authenticity of the products they buy.

4.6. Expected Outcomes

ProofPoint system will largely reduce the situation of counterfeit merchandise in the market. It offers an open and trusted Fig. 4. Collaborative Diagram platform where consumers can be sure whether the products they are purchasing are genuine or not. In the system, it is possible for businesses to prevent the counterfeiting of their brands in a very improved way. Hence, verification of genuineness by consumers will be done confidently without risking being coned by counterfeiters. The system is dynamic due to the integration of AI technologies, reacting promptly to emerging threats. It makes it possible for the system to stay robust as global supply chains face continuously changing challenges. With advance anomaly detection and predictive analytics, the system identifies emerging fraud activities and takes necessary steps proactively, ensuring further confidence building for both consumers and manufacturers. In general, the ProofPoint system is definitely an integral tool in the war against fake goods and, hence, authenticity and reliability in the market [1], [6].

Fig. 3 Collaborative Diagram of ProofPoint System

5. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The ProofPoint system employed a blend of blockchain technology, smart contracts, and a local database to track product authenticity and ownership. This section provides insights into the technical aspects of the system, its development, and the results obtained during testing.

5.1. System Implementation

The ProofPoint system is meticulously designed to provide a seamless and secure solution for product authenticity verification and ownership tracking, combining advanced front-end development, blockchain integration, smart contracts, a local database, and a user-friendly mobile application. The system's front-end is developed using the ReactJS library, which offers efficiency in creating dynamic, responsive interfaces. This ensures users can interact with the platform effortlessly, including scanning QR codes and accessing real-time product information.

By prioritizing user experience, the interface is designed to be intuitive and accessible for both businesses and consumers, facilitating smooth navigation and efficient use of the system [3]. At its core, the Proofpoint system utilises the Ethereum blockchain for its reliable and immutable storage capabilities. Ethereum is selected for its robust ecosystem and proven support for smart contracts, making it an ideal platform for building decentralised applications. Through the integration of Web3.js, the front end seamlessly communicates with the blockchain, ensuring that smart contracts execute flawlessly and blockchain records are retrieved efficiently. These smart contracts, written in Solidity and deployed using the Remix IDE, are critical components of the system. They automate vital processes such as product registration, ownership transfer, and verification, eliminating the need for intermediaries and providing secure, transparent, and tamper-proof transactions [9]. To address the challenge of efficiently storing and accessing large amounts of metadata, ProofPoint employs a hybrid architecture that integrates a local database alongside the blockchain. This database stores non-critical information, such as product descriptions, specifications, and images, ensuring that essential product data can be accessed quickly without burdening the blockchain. The local database is synchronised with the blockchain, enabling real-time updates of product records and maintaining the integrity and reliability of the data.

This approach strikes a balance between the blockchain's immutability and the database's speed, resulting in a highly efficient and scalable system [8]. Enhancing the system's accessibility and usability is a mobile application that serves as a key interface for consumers and stakeholders. This application allows users to scan product-specific QR codes, which are linked to blockchain records, providing instant access to detailed information such as authenticity status, ownership history, and relevant certifications. By offering this feature, the ProofPoint mobile app empowers consumers to verify product authenticity before making a purchase, fostering trust and transparency in the supply chain. The app's user-friendly design ensures that it is easy to use, making advanced blockchain technology accessible to individuals with minimal technical expertise [10]. Overall, the ProofPoint system combines state-of-the-art technologies and innovative design principles to address the persistent issue of counterfeiting in global supply chains. Its integration of ReactJS, Ethereum blockchain, smart contracts, a hybrid database architecture, and a mobile application creates a powerful and reliable platform that enhances efficiency, security, and transparency. By leveraging these technologies, ProofPoint not only simplifies product verification and ownership tracking but also provides a scalable solution that can adapt to various industries, ensuring widespread applicability and long-term sustainability [3], [8], [9], [10].

5.2. Results and Performance Analysis

A comprehensive scalability test was conducted on the ProofPoint system to assess its performance in terms of scalability, security, user experience, and cost-efficiency. The system exhibited acceptable latency while managing a high volume of product registrations and ownership transfers, thanks to the integration of a local database that maintained smooth performance even as transaction volumes increased. However, the scalability is currently constrained by Ethereum's limited transaction throughput, prompting plans to incorporate layer-2 solutions like rollups in future iterations to enhance system capacity. Security was a standout feature, with smart contracts ensuring tamper-proof and secure transactions that effectively blocked counterfeit products from infiltrating the supply chain. The decentralized nature of the blockchain further bolstered security by providing immutable product records that are immune to unauthorized modifications. User feedback highlighted the system's positive impact on user experience, with consumers appreciating the convenience of QR code scanning for real-time verification of product authenticity.

Businesses also benefited from the system's efficiency, as smart contracts automated critical processes, reducing delays and minimizing errors. On the cost-efficiency front, the ProofPoint system significantly lowered operational costs by eliminating intermediaries and automating tasks.

However, Ethereum's high gas fees pose a challenge, particularly for smaller businesses, spurring the exploration of hybrid blockchain models or alternative platforms to reduce transaction costs. While the system holds great promise, certain challenges persist, particularly regarding scalability and transaction fees. To address these, future developments will focus on integrating advanced blockchain technologies like layer-2 solutions to improve throughput and affordability, ensuring the system's adaptability and sustainability in diverse use cases.

6. CONCLUSION

The ProofPoint system has demonstrated itself as a highly effective solution for combating counterfeiting, offering a robust approach to real-time product verification and secure ownership tracking. By leveraging the power of blockchain technology, smart contracts, and an integrated local database, ProofPoint strikes a perfect balance between security, performance, and efficiency. The system ensures tamper-proof records and transparent tracking across the entire supply chain, making it an invaluable tool for industries where counterfeiting poses significant risks, such as pharmaceuticals, electronics, and luxury goods. Its scalable architecture enables seamless integration across diverse sectors, adapting to the specific needs of various industries. Through its advanced features, ProofPoint not only enhances product authentication and ownership verification but also plays a crucial role in restoring consumer trust and confidence. By minimizing the risk of counterfeit products, businesses can protect their brand integrity, reduce financial losses, and foster a more transparent and secure marketplace. As the system continues to evolve, its potential to transform the way industries tackle counterfeiting and fraud remains immense, offering long-term solutions that strengthen supply chain resilience and build lasting consumer relationships.

7. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

The ProofPoint system offers a comprehensive solution to the long-standing problem of counterfeiting by leveraging blockchain, smart contracts, and a local database. This system ensures secure ownership tracking, real-time product verification, and efficient data management, effectively preventing counterfeit goods from entering the supply chain. However, there are further opportunities to enhance the system using Artificial Intelligence (AI) and advanced database integrations.

7.1. Discussion

The system's decentralized and tamper-proof ledger for product transactions, powered by blockchain, offers significant improvements in transparency. The use of smart contracts automates critical processes, eliminating intermediaries and minimizing operational delays. Non-critical metadata, such as product descriptions and specifications, is stored on a local database, ensuring fast access to essential information without overburdening the blockchain.

User feedback has indicated improvements in trust and transparency. Consumers appreciate the convenience of verifying product authenticity through QR codes, while businesses benefit from the automated transfer of ownership, which reduces errors and enhances efficiency. However, scalability remains a challenge due to the limitations of the Ethereum blockchain. High gas fees are also a concern, especially for small businesses operating with limited margins. Counterfeiters continuously evolve their methods, creating new challenges for businesses.

Integrating AI into the ProofPoint system could further enhance its adaptability by detecting anomalies and predicting fraud risks. Additionally, predictive analytics would allow companies to anticipate vulnerabilities in their supply chains, strengthening the system's defenses against emerging threats.

7.2. Future Work

Future iterations of the ProofPoint system will incorporate AI-driven algorithms to enhance security and optimize supply chain management. Machine learning models will analyze transactions in real time, identifying irregular patterns and flagging suspicious activities. Predictive analytics will pinpoint areas most vulnerable to counterfeiting, allowing businesses to allocate resources more effectively.

To address scalability concerns, the system will explore the use of layer-2 solutions, such as rollups or sidechains. These technologies will increase system throughput and reduce transaction fees, ensuring the system can handle higher volumes of transactions without compromising performance.

The database architecture will also be improved through a hybrid model that combines distributed databases with blockchain. This approach will provide better scalability and faster access to product information. Federated learning techniques will be employed to maintain data privacy while allowing AI models to learn from decentralized datasets without sharing sensitive information.

In summary, the future of the ProofPoint system looks promising. By integrating advanced technologies such as AI, optimized databases, and blockchain enhancements, the system will remain adaptable and scalable, offering a sustainable solution for combating counterfeiting across industries

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Citation: Vraj Shah, Mahir Modi, Manas Raval. (2024). From Origin to End: Blockchain for Seamless Product Authentication and Ownership Verification. International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology, 15(6), 46–57.

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